

Milestone:

MS24 - Annual workshop on data quality: submission processes - 2 of 2

Lead Participant:

THL

Author:

Markus Perola, Tero Hiekkalinna

Due:

June 2025

Date Of Completion:

June 18, 2025

Means of Verification

Workshop was held on 18th June and agenda/meeting minutes/notes and presentations are here (<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fulZRVbGKC/V2AUW9zcaaDdKtHeprI-xZFip9ep1bQns/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.f09w24tvode9>)

Zoom recording of the meeting here (https://drive.google.com/file/d/1DSxGNiD_wBxpJQ1GqYPiTXjwfvlymmOl/view?usp=drive_link).

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

Talks by Regina Becker, Ivo Gut and Jeroen Belien and total of ~47 online participants.

List of participants in meeting minutes.

Next action steps

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